

GENERAL CONCEPT OF TEACHING METHODS

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Abstract. *Teaching methods are the broader techniques used to help students achieve learning outcomes, while activities are the different ways of implementing these methods. This article discusses about some features and peculiarities of teaching methods which are one of the most important issues in didactics. The main functions of teaching methods are also considered, which include managerial and executive ones.*

Keywords: *teaching methods, learning activity, learning tool, independent learning activity, learning opportunities.*

The problem of teaching methods is one of the most important issues in didactics. The effectiveness of all areas of teaching can be estimated by addressing these issues properly. A young teacher who is just starting out has a hard time guiding students from ignorance to learning. What is the way, method or tool that provides children with deep, independent, comprehensive knowledge, leads to creative thinking, independent learning activities? Teaching methods solve this problem.

Accordingly, teaching methods are a set of ways and means that serve to enable teachers and students to work together actively to address educational challenges.

At the same time, one can see the diversity of definitions of the term “teaching method” in pedagogical sources. Here are some of them [3]:

<p>The method of teaching is a method of interaction of teachers and students aimed at achieving educational goals at the modern level V.I. Zagvyazinsky</p>	<p>Teaching methods are a complex component of the learning process, which serves to illuminate all areas of teacher and student activities, creating a large number of connections and connections between them. (G.I.Shukina)</p>	<p>Teaching methods are the methods of organizing educational activities to find solutions to various didactic problems aimed at the teacher's teaching and the acquisition of teaching materials by students (I.F.Kharlamov)</p>	<p>The method of teaching is a system of actions with a specific content, an algorithm that ensures the achievement of the set goal (P.I.Podlasiy)</p>
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Figure 1. Some definitions of the term “teaching method”

There is also the idea that it is a way for teachers and students to interact in an orderly way.

Teaching methods first appear in the minds of educators as a generalized project of activities in a particular area. This project is introduced into practice as a set of specific actions, practices or methods for the interaction of teacher and student activities, teaching and learning. The method does not take other forms, because the method of education itself, in general, represents a didactic model of activity.

The teaching method acts as a multidimensional phenomenon, as the core of the educational process. It is a mechanism for implementing the set goals, largely determines the final results of the learning process. In order to confidently predict the desired result, the teacher must professionally master the methods of activity. Teaching methods should contribute to the

activation of students' cognitive activity, should be correctly selected, and should not allow students to be overloaded in class [2].

Attempts to define a definition that fully illuminates the essence of the concept are still being made, and new definitions are being put forward. However, despite the fact that there are different views on the essence of the concept of "teaching methods", there is a commonality that brings them closer. Most authors agree that "teaching methods are ways to organize students' learning activities." This means that teaching methods are a set of methods that are used in the educational process and ensure its effectiveness.

Teaching methods serve to illuminate the purpose of education, through which the ways of mastering the content of education are expressed, the interaction of teachers and students, the characteristics are reflected.

While the method is seen as a means of achieving an educational goal on the one hand, it is a prerequisite for the implementation of managed learning activities on the other.

Teaching methods are always introduced with the help of one or another learning tool, so it should be noted that they are interdependent.

The structure of the teaching method is a systematically organized set of methodological techniques that ensure the successful implementation of its functions.

A methodological technique is a structural element of a teaching method that sets the order of actions of subjects in the learning process. And in this sense, teaching method is a system of methodological techniques that, in accordance with specific educational goals, regulates the order of actions of the teacher and student aimed at transmitting and assimilating the necessary educational information.

One of the most striking features of teaching methods is their dualism (duality), which is manifested not even in the fact that two subjects with different goals and activities participate in its implementation. The duality of teaching method is reflected in the fact that the system-forming factor in its structure is the constructive unity of the methods of working with information and the elements that provide it (from the objective side) and the methods of organizing its interiorization (from the subjective side), that is, the unity of the objective and subjective in the method.

Thus, the structure of teaching method includes:

– from the objective side of the teaching method: techniques that ensure the transmission of educational information; techniques for correcting the methods of presenting educational information; techniques that facilitate working with information (techniques for visualizing information);

– from the subjective side of the teaching method: techniques for stimulating and maintaining motivation for learning, including techniques that teach goal setting; techniques for activating educational activity; techniques that facilitate the systematic implementation of educational activities; techniques for organizing the formation of necessary educational skills, abilities and methods of action; techniques for organizing feedback; techniques that ensure reflexive awareness of the results of the activity.

Teaching methods are ambiguous in nature. It is:

A. Information and management;

B. Performance of reading, learning, teaching, supervision and self-monitoring tasks.

Each method consists of a number of elements, which are called methods, and it increases the efficiency of this method.

For example, in the exercise method, the student analyzes the work done, points out mistakes, and so on. Exercise here is a method; analysis is a way to point out mistakes.

Thus, the method, as a set of effective methods, performs a number of didactic tasks: introduces new material, acquires knowledge and skills, strengthens them, is used in practice.

The teaching method always performs two important functions: managerial and executive.

The unique aspect of management in the teaching method is that the teacher must be able to manage and know both the internal and external aspects of \ student's activities.

Often, the external side of student's activity (the student observes, reads, hears, performs certain tasks) does not reflect the relationship of the internal side of the process, student's activity is clear in understanding, comprehending, directly influencing it will not appear.

From this point of view, the problem of teaching methods is the inner essence of the process, the ability to see the quality aspects, to stimulate active, independent activity in the student, to turn that material into his own needs. The pedagogical nature of addressing this is one of the most important challenges facing teaching methods.

Another unique aspect of teaching methods is related to student's attitude, changes in attitudes, and, consequently, the correction of the process.

Another peculiarity of teaching methods is that they lead the child from ignorance to cognition, and then teach him to organize independent learning activities. The same problem is the main problem with the teaching method.

A number of tools are in place to increase the effectiveness of teaching methods.

A tool is anything, an event, an impact process, etc. that helps to equip, improve, and increase the effectiveness of a learning process.

For example, books: (textbooks, manuals, programmed textbooks, notebooks, etc.); visual aids; specially equipped cabinets, laboratory rooms; technical means; the image of the teacher, and others. These is a complex way helping increase the effectiveness of this or that method.

There are a number of pedagogical requirements that must be followed when selecting and applying teaching methods:

1. Teaching methods should be in accordance with the principles of education.
2. Teaching methods should be chosen depending on the goals and objectives of education.
3. Teaching methods are selected according to the content of education, the nature of the material.
4. These methods are suitable for students' knowledge, learning opportunities (age, physical, mental); selected according to the level of preparation, the specifics of the class team.
5. It depends on the circumstances and the time allotted for training.
6. It depends on the capabilities of the teacher, i.e. the experience gained, theoretical and practical training, personal and professional qualities.

The possibilities of modern pedagogical technologies are limitless and are aimed at improving the educational, upbringing and applied aspects of the process. A scientific approach to the problem is necessary to eliminate the problem of formally obtaining a certificate, promotes the emergence of motivation to obtain new knowledge, improves the direction of education in general.

Thus, the choice of teaching methods is determined by the goals and objectives of teaching, the content and methods of a given science and a given subject, taking into account a specific topic, the educational capabilities of children (both age and their level of preparation, characteristics of the class); characteristics of external conditions; the capabilities of the teacher

(his experience, level of preparation, personal characteristics); the effectiveness of teaching methods (how effective the method used is in a given situation).

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